

A NEW METHOD OF PREPARATION OF ACETO- AND BENZONITRILES.

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p-Toluene sulphonyl chloride may be used as a dehydrating agent in the preparation of nitriles from acid amides. The advantage of the process is that the yield is better and the reagent is less drastic.

Benzonitrile.—Benzamide (12 g.) and dry *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (19 g.), were intimately mixed and heated under reflux at 130-35° (oil-bath) for 1½ hours. The mixture was then distilled in steam for the isolation of benzonitrile which was then redistilled (7·3 g.).

p-Toluenesulphonic acid can be recovered from the non-volatile residue.

Acetonitrile.—Similarly, acetamide (10 g.) gave with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (31 g.) after interaction and isolation in the manner described, acetonitrile (5 g.).

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